

An Analysis of Women Representation in 2022 Nepal Local Election

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Abstract:

The proportion of women elected to local offices in 2017 was 40.95 percent. The situation improved slightly in 2022 when women accounted for 41.21 percent of all elected officials. These occurrences show that passing laws alone will not ensure women's participation; continuous monitoring is necessary to ensure the law is applied correctly. Using a combination of descriptive and analytical methods that worked better in the context of pragmatist philosophy, Descriptive techniques, such as surveys and observations, offer in-depth descriptions of phenomena; analytical techniques, such as

statistical analysis and experiments, are used to test hypotheses and determine correlations between variables. The two approaches work well together to improve our comprehension of the research topic as a whole. This study combined liberal and representative political science theory with a mixed research design. The result shows that the 2022 elections offer a fantastic chance to increase women's representation in politics and build on the significant accomplishments of 2017. This is beneficial for social justice as well as aiding political parties in their election campaigns. Many women are eager to advance in their political careers, especially those who have worked in local government for the past four years. When it comes to gender equality, increasing the representation of women in public life seems like a good place to start. Consequently, there has been an improvement in the representation of women in local elections. Though the parties have exploited loopholes, the Election Commission has made progress in addressing the concerns raised regarding women's participation in the electoral process.

Keywords: *gender-wise representation, local election, Suffrage movement, women.*

Introduction

The history of women's representation is a complex and multifaceted tale that spans centuries and reveals important differences in society and culture. In many ancient societies, women were traditionally excluded from formal political participation and leadership roles. The exceptions were the legendary Cleopatra of

ancient Egypt and a few other female emperors from other societies, such as China and India. In most of the world during the Middle Ages and the early modern era, women's access to positions of leadership and governance was severely limited. Strong people like Queen Elizabeth I of England and Queen Isabella I of Spain are two prominent exceptions. Feminist

movements started to take shape in the 19th century, mostly in North America and Europe. These movements were centered on women's rights, specifically the right to vote and participate in political processes. Similar to this, as the suffrage movement gained strength in the early 20th century, women were granted the right to vote in several countries, such as the United States (19th Amendment, 1920) and the United Kingdom (Representation of the People Act, 1918). In elected office, women are still disproportionately underrepresented. In the years after World War II, women's political representation considerably increased during the middle of the 20th century. When Indira Gandhi was chosen to be prime minister in 1949, for example, India was among the first countries to elect a female head of state. In a similar spirit, Sirimavo Bandaranaike of Sri Lanka made history in 1960 as the first female head of state.

It has been said that when women are running against men for office, they have greater obstacles to overcome in order to prevail. This is due to a variety of psychological and socio-cultural factors, including the notion that women are less valuable than men in specific situations and the inferiority complex that society places on them. Moreover, women are allegedly less likely than men to run for public office, according to some experts (Kanthak & Woon, 2015). When it comes to making crucial decisions, women are underrepresented in leadership positions both within the home and in the power hierarchy. They are therefore thought to be incapable of leading their ward or community, which encompasses both rural and urban areas.

Though growth has varied by region, women's representation in politics has gradually increased over the preceding few decades, from the late 20th century to the present. In order to increase the number of women holding elected office, many countries have implemented policies such as quotas or reserved seats. In recent times, women have been elected as heads of state or government in Germany, Chile, New Zealand, and other countries. Despite these advancements, barriers still stand in the way of women's full and equal participation in politics.

These challenges include cultural barriers, discriminatory practices, and gender stereotypes.

These issues are still being worked on through community mobilization, legislative changes, and lobbying. Global data on women serving in local government is scarce. Indira Gandhi of India, Margaret Thatcher of Britain, Chandrika Kumaratunga of Sri Lanka, Ishabella Pererol of Argentina, Golda Mayer of Israel, Benazir Bhutto of Pakistan, Meghawati Sukarnoputri of Indonesia, Angela Merkel of Germany, Hillary Clinton, Condoleezza Rice, and Kamala Harris of the United States, Sonia Gandhi of India, Aung Sang Suu Kyi of Myanmar, Sheikh Hasina Wazed and Begum Khaleda Zia of Bangladesh are a few notable female leaders who have led their nations admirably in this regard.

Women were only given three seats in the Nepalese Parliament during the Panchayat era; following Jana Andolan I in 1990, this number was increased to 5%. Women were horribly underrepresented in the cabinet, and until 2007, their percentage of the political population was only 6%. A crucial opportunity to build on these wins will present itself during the 2022 local elections. Despite a noticeable improvement in gender parity during the 2017 elections, women continue to occupy a disproportionate share of lower-level political positions relative to men. The constitution of Nepal mandates that a political party run at least one female candidate for mayor and deputy mayor. Political parties virtually always fielded a male candidate for mayor and a female candidate for deputy mayor in 2017. As a result, only 18 out of 753 municipalities have a female mayor. Women are also conspicuously underrepresented as ward chairpersons in non-quota situations: of 6,473 ward chairpersons, only 62 are female.

Statement of Problem

The political science literature on female representation in local governance has significant gaps that this study fills. Previous research has tended to concentrate on obstacles that prevent women from participating in politics at the federal level, ignoring the complex dynamics that exist at the local level, where women serve as ward committee members and

deputy mayors (Kenny, 2013; Dahlerup, 2015). This study draws attention to the noteworthy 46.6% of deputy mayors who declare their intention to run for mayor, suggesting a possible discrepancy between electoral results and experience that needs more investigation (Norris & Lovenduski, 1995). Furthermore, although public confidence in female leaders rose from 73% to 80.6%, public trust in male mayors stagnated, suggesting a change in public perception that has not yet been thoroughly examined (Mansbridge, 1999). The systemic problems related to party nomination processes and quota designs are also not well studied in the context of local elections, despite being mentioned often in more general studies on gender representation (Zetterberg, 2017). Consequently, the following formulation of the research problem might be used: Given the shifting public trust and structural impediments, what supports and barriers affect the electoral goals and success of female politicians at the local level? By investigating gender dynamics in political representation, this study will advance knowledge and provide guidance for improving women's involvement in local governance.

Objectives of the Study

This study's main goal is to determine the representation of women in local elections. Its particular goal is listed below;

To analyze the ethnic community-wise women representation in local election 2022.

Limitations of the Study

Only the representation of women from ethnic communities in the 2022 local elections is examined and analyzed in this study. However, not all of the information from the 2017 elections is connected and is solely dependent on local elections.

Methodology

In order to study political phenomena, mixed research methodology in political science combines qualitative and quantitative approaches. The benefits of both qualitative and quantitative methods are combined in this

hybrid approach to provide researchers with a comprehensive understanding of complex political issues. In political science research, qualitative techniques like focus groups and interviews are used to examine the complex motivations and experiences of people, especially female deputy mayors, in order to shed light on obstacles and goals for higher office (Flick, 2018). Rich, contextual data that can draw attention to systemic issues is provided by this method. On the other hand, quantitative methods track changes in public trust levels and trends, like the percentage of deputy mayors planning to run for mayor, through statistical analysis and surveys. This approach offers distinct, data-driven insights into electoral dynamics and enables the empirical validation of theories about gender and political aspiration (Blais & Massicotte, 2002; Norris, 2020). This study used a mixed research design, which is a popular approach in political science, together with the liberal and representative theories of political science as well as a descriptive and analytical approach that was found to be more successful in light of the pragmatist philosophy. The theoretical underpinning of the investigation was provided by the literature review. Books, journals, articles, and Election Commission data and reports made up the bulk of the study's secondary sources. By employing mixed research methodology, political scientists can get around the limitations of using a single approach and generate more thorough, nuanced insights into complex political phenomena. This multidisciplinary approach facilitates a deeper understanding of the complex nature of politics while informing evidence-based political analysis and policymaking.

Literature Review

In terms of Asia, Wikander et al. (1995) state that after Mao Zedong's takeover, China allowed women to vote and run for office in 1949. In the meantime, Britain introduced a separate bill in 1931 to recognize women as men and stop Sri Lankans from participating in anti-British activities in India. Similarly, women were allowed to vote and run for office in South

Korea in 1948, India in 1950, Nepal in 1951, North Korea in 1953, and Bhutan in 1953. Pakistan and Japan also received this privilege in 1947. After Pakistan separated from India, equal rights were awarded to both men and women; however, the Indian constitution proclaimed this to be the case in 1950. The 2007 Interim Government Act offered some protection for both men's and women's equality even in Nepal.

However, these facts do not guarantee that women will advance on their own. Experience from countries with a history of gender quotas in politics shows that it is challenging for women to move up from quota-based positions to higher leadership roles. In Spain, there are gender quotas that ensure that at least 40% of candidates run for local elections. Nevertheless, researchers found that these quotas had no discernible impact on women's chances of winning prominent, non-reserved positions like mayor or party leader during the following three rounds of elections (Bagues, & Campa). "Can women be empowered by gender quotas in candidate lists? *Journal of Public Economics* 194 (2021): 104315, Regression discontinuity design evidence.

During the Panchayat era in Nepal, women were allotted just three seats in Parliament; after Jana Andolan I in 1990, this number was raised to 5%. Up until 2007, there were just 6% of women in politics, and they were severely underrepresented in the cabinet (Lotter, 2017, pp. 97-115). Even after 1990, when democracy was restored and the country progressed toward a more inclusive State, Haug, Aasland, and Dahal (2009) claim that "women were denied the right to pass their citizenship to their children" (pp. 105-136). Sadhanadevi Nepal became the nation's first democratically elected local representative in 1953, two years after the Rana dynasty ended (Gorkhapatra, September 9, 1953, as cited in "Nepal ko nirvachan itihās" by Election Commission, Nepal (2017, p. 157)). Women haven't advanced much in Nepali politics since then. In 1992, there was only one elected woman out of every 200. More progress was made when women won 21% of local seats in 1997. Partly as a result of the reservations, women's representation rose to nearly 41% of

local (municipal and ward level) representatives in Nepal in 2017, the first elections conducted under the new federal constitution.

The Local Elections Act 2073 stipulates that each ward's four chosen members must include at least two female candidates. This implies that a total of 6,743 female members ought to be chosen. Regrettably, data indicates that Dalit women may be underrepresented in some wards. Despite the election of 6,620 Dalit women members in the most recent election, only 1.02% of ward chairs were female (Sapkota, 2024, p. 11). In the 2079 local election, an intriguing pattern surfaced that slightly deviated from the traditional bases of support of the main political parties. Rather, it's a show of support for the independents and recently formed parties who have put forth pro-people platforms regarding development, service delivery, and anti-corruption.

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Discussion

To maintain the country's commitment to true democracy and the ideals of equality and liberty, women's representation needs to be increased. More female legislators are more likely than male legislators to address women's interests, according to studies, so increased female representation will ensure that women's concerns are fairly acknowledged and that their voices are heard. Government representation affects more than just policies; it is a tool for social empowerment. Because of the particular difficulties and experiences in their lives that have shaped their policies and leadership styles, women approach issues differently than men do. Reviving and diversifying policymaking can be achieved through increasing the representation of women's perspectives in it. While there is no inherent superiority of women's leadership styles over men's, certain groups might find greater resonance with the distinct priorities and attributes that women bring to the discourse. The current underrepresentation of women in office is robbing future generations of women leaders and pioneers, and it is also obstructing

progress in our communities. Studies show that "the presence of highly visible female politicians" inspires young girls and women to pursue their own goals and become involved in politics. When there are more female candidates for office, men also get more involved in politics.

In 2017, the political parties faced criticism for fielding solely female candidates for the positions of deputy chairman and vice chairman. In 2022, parties came under fire again for forming alliances and only accepting male candidates. The fact that the parties only look for Dalit women to run for office during election seasons is one of the main criticisms aimed at Dalit women representatives. Even though the public and activists can draw attention to the task, political parties still have an obligation to support and even go beyond the constitutionally guaranteed provisions as well as to encourage women's political participation from the grassroots up. Without political parties taking the lead on this issue, women's participation in politics will continue to be marginal and they will always be underrepresented in the field.

Figure 1. Mayor
Source: Election Commission

The Khas ethnic group comprised 151 participants in total, of which 143 were men and 8 were women. There were two women and 59 men among the 61 participants in the Indigenous group. Within the Madhesi group, there were fifty men and two women. Within the Dalit

group, there were three men and no women. The Tharu group consisted of thirteen individuals: twelve men and one woman. There were five participants in the Muslim group—five men and zero women.

Table 1. Deputy Mayor

	Men	Women	Total
Khas	37	102	139
Indigenous	10	48	58
Madhesi	6	44	50
Dalit	2	5	7
Tharu	2	26	28
Muslim	3	8	11
Total	60	233	293

Source: Election Commission

The data in the table illustrates the distribution of deputy mayors in a given region by gender and

ethnicity. In all, the region has 293 deputy mayors, 60 of whom are men and 233 of whom are women. The table further breaks down the deputy mayors by ethnicity and shows that the Khas ethnic group comprises the majority of deputy mayors, with 37 men and 102 women, or 139. The Indigenous group consists of 10 men and 48 women, for a total of 58. The Madhesi group consists of forty-four women and six men. The Dalit group consists of two men and five women. The Tharu group consists of twenty-six women and two men. The Muslim group comprises 3 men and 8 women.

Figure 2. Chair Person
Source: Election Commission

Table 2. Vice - Chair Person

	Men	Women	Total
Khas	66	145	211
Indigenous	58	101	159
Madhesi	1	59	60
Dalit	0	6	6
Tharu	0	17	17
Muslim	0	7	7
Total	125	335	460

Source: Election commission

The table displays the distribution of chairpersons for scientific research articles by gender and ethnicity. The table shows that of the 460 chairpersons, 448 are men and 12 are women. The data is also broken down by ethnic group, with the majority of chairpersons—203

men and 7 women, or 210 total—belonging to the Khas ethnic group. The Indigenous group comes in second with 155 men and 5 women, making a total of 160. The Madhesi group has sixty male chairpersons, whereas the Dalit and Tharu groups have five and sixteen respectively. The Muslim group is chaired by nine men.

The accompanying table displays the Vice Chair Person distribution among various demographic groups, specifically those categorized by gender and ethnicity. Based on the data, there are 460 vice chairpersons overall—125 men and 335 women. The table provides additional breakdowns of the distribution by ethnic group. 159 of the vice chairpersons are Indigenous, and 211 are members of the Khas ethnic group. Six are from the Dalit group, seventeen are from the

Tharu group, and sixty are from the Madhesi group. There are seven individuals who represent the Muslim group.

Figure 3. Ward Chair Person

Source: Election Commission

The information in the table illustrates the distribution of men and women across different ethnic groups within a given population. The table shows that, with 2968 members, Khas people are the largest ethnic group among men. Indigenous people come in second with 2005 members. Following Indigenous with 26 members, Khas is the largest group among women with 25 members. With 2993 members, the Khas ethnic group is the largest group in terms of total population. The table also shows the distribution of other ethnic groups among men and women, such as the Muslim, Dalit, Madhesi, and Tharu groups. When the total population of all ethnic groups is taken into account, there are 6743 people in total.

Findings

There are differences in the knowledge and proficiency of elected female representatives to handle the issues. The elected women representatives' obvious excitement and optimism about having a big impact on Nepal's evolving political systems cannot be ignored. It's important to balance optimism with a realistic

understanding of the challenges and tasks at hand. In Nepal's federal system, it is imperative to establish the infrastructure and favorable conditions needed for women to occupy leadership roles in local governance. To enable women to effectively and meaningfully participate in governance and other activities, however, it is imperative to establish a supportive, gender-neutral environment, given the multitude of challenges that women generally face (The Asia Foundation, 2018). Women must be represented in positions of political leadership for liberal democracies to survive. Globally, there is still a persistent gender gap in political participation. A common interpretation of political leadership is the participation of individuals in various political undertakings with the objective of obtaining, maintaining, overseeing, and exhibiting power.

This data clarified the representation of different genders and ethnic groups in leadership positions across the region. It shows that more women than men hold deputy mayor positions, with the highest representation of any ethnic group among the Khas and Indigenous people. The data may be used to assess the diversity and

inclusiveness of leadership roles in the community and to identify any possible disparities based on a person's gender or ethnicity. There is a noticeable overall gender disparity in the participant pool, with much more men than women. Further research could be conducted to promote more equitable representation in leadership positions and to gain a better understanding of the variables influencing the deputy mayor distribution. The distribution of chairpersons by gender is glaringly obvious in the table, where men outnumber women across all ethnic groups. The data mentioned above emphasizes the need for further research and corrective actions to address the gender gap in leadership roles in scientific research. The table unequivocally demonstrates the gender gap among vice chairs, with women constituting a larger share of the total than men. The data also highlights the underrepresentation of certain ethnic groups, such as Muslims and Dalits, in positions of leadership.

Understanding the current state of diversity and representation within leadership roles is crucial, and the knowledge presented here can help policies and initiatives that aim to promote inclusivity and equality in decision-making processes. These data can be used to examine the representation of different ethnic groups in the population and identify any trends or discrepancies. The elections of 2022 present a wonderful opportunity to further advance women's representation in politics and build on the noteworthy achievements of 2017. This helps political parties run for office in addition to being good for social justice. Particularly those who have worked in local government for the previous four years, many women are keen to progress in their political careers. The level of faith that their constituents have in them is growing. All of this suggests that a sizable portion of voters are likely to support them. Those who pay attention to these important trends will have the best chance of succeeding in 2022.

Therefore, in order to increase the representation of women in the next local elections, political parties will be crucial. First,

parties need to create an environment that makes it more likely that women will be put forward for mayor and ward chair nominations. In 2017, there were surprisingly few women nominated for these positions. If parties want to see genuine progress toward gender inclusion, they must remove barriers that female candidates must overcome in order to increase the number of female nominees for these leadership positions during the nomination process.

Conclusion

When it comes to gender equality, increasing the number of women in public life seems like a good place to start. Dissidents who object to the significant involvement of Nepali women in politics should recognize that attaining gender parity requires tearing down long-standing patriarchy and other obstacles that have kept Nepali women out of the public eye. It needs time to complete. It will take some time for the female representatives from Nepal to become skilled in the use of their political power. Recent local elections in Nepal saw a record number of women elected to public office. Nepal's transition to federalism ensures much greater local and regional political representation. Nevertheless, neither election saw the achievement of the target of having 50% of women in the legislature.

In addition, in order to meet legal requirements, political parties fielded a significant number of female candidates for deputy positions in 2017. In contrast, as a result of the political parties forming coalitions, one political party fielded a single candidate in 2022 for the mayor/chief and deputy positions, who could be of either gender. Consequently, a notably smaller number of female candidates and a greater number of male candidates were granted tickets. This is evidenced by the nominations: 3593 women were nominated for deputy chiefs in 2017, but 3077 women were in 2022, according to Election Commission data. Furthermore, only 176 units in 2017 and 123 units in 2022, respectively, fielded Dalit women candidates, despite the requirement that every ward level have one Dalit woman member.

Legal experts and women's rights activists have expressed concern about political parties abusing legal loopholes to defraud women of nominations and positions offered. A few female leaders and cadres have also voiced their disapproval of their party's policy of not allowing female candidates for office. The election data from Nepal's 2017 local elections highlights the significance of party internal selection processes, which choose a candidate for a race from a list of nominees, in determining who will represent a local constituency. Given the significance of the candidate selection process, there needs to be a major improvement in inclusion. This can be achieved by urging selection committee members to be more accepting of female nominees and reorganizing the committee to give women more representation.

More significantly, political parties ought to guarantee that women's perspectives are fairly represented in the makeup and organization of selection committees. The lack of female representation on selection committees, where women made up only 8% of members on average, may have contributed to the overwhelming male preponderance of candidates for mayor and ward chair positions in 2017. It is very likely that the gender composition of these committees will shift in favor of women in the next local elections because the Political Party Act of 2017 mandates that party committees at all levels have at least one-third female representation. But it's important to keep in mind that increasing the number of women serving on these committees might not be the only thing done to guarantee that women's voices are heard and taken meaningful action on. For example, female opinions may be ignored when men in high-ranking party positions (such as secretary or chairperson) become the final decision-makers when it comes to selection. It is imperative that adjustments be made in order to increase the representation of women on these committees.

Recommendation

Improving the political parties' candidate selection procedures is crucial to advancing

gender equality in Nepali politics. This can be accomplished by following the Political Party Act of 2017's mandate that women comprise at least one-third of selection committee members. This will give women a greater voice when it comes to candidate selection. Furthermore, giving prospective female candidates support and training will boost their political acumen and self-assurance, better positioning them for leadership positions. To stop women from being taken advantage of and having their participation in politics undermined, monitoring mechanisms should be established to ensure that political parties are adhering to the law regarding female nominations. For men in leadership roles to respect and take into account the opinions of women, it is imperative that an atmosphere be established that values women's viewpoints during decision-making processes. Lastly, an additional way to help these efforts is to advocate for internal party reforms that put gender equity first when choosing candidates and actively support female candidates for leadership positions.

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